

OUTLINE THE PROFITABILITY ANALYSIS SELECTED FERTILIZERS COMPANY IN TAMILNADU

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Abstract-The profitability of selected fertilizer companies in Tamil Nadu, specifically SPIC and MFL, through various financial ratios. The focus is on Operating Profit Ratio, Net Profit Ratio, Return on Net Worth, Total Debt/Equity, and Return on Assets to evaluate the financial performance and operational efficiency of these firms. The analysis reveals significant differences in profitability metrics between the two companies, providing insights into their operational strategies and financial health. By examining these ratios, the research aims to highlight the factors influencing profitability in the fertilizer sector, emphasizing the importance of effective financial management. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the competitive landscape in the fertilizer industry and offer recommendations for improving profitability in similar firms.

Key Words: Profitability, Fertilizer Industry, Financial Ratios

Introduction- The fertilizer industry plays a crucial role in enhancing agricultural productivity and ensuring food security, particularly in agrarian economies like India. Tamil Nadu, with its diverse agricultural practices, hosts several prominent fertilizer companies, including Southern Petrochemicals Industries Corporation (SPIC) and Madras Fertilizers Limited (MFL). Understanding the profitability of these companies is vital for stakeholders, including investors, management, and policymakers. This paper aims to analyze the profitability of SPIC and MFL by employing financial ratios that provide insights into their operational efficiency and financial stability. These ratios are essential for assessing the companies' performance and capital structure. By analyzing these metrics, this study seeks to identify trends and benchmarks within the Tamil Nadu fertilizer sector, ultimately contributing to improved financial decision-making and strategic planning for these firms.

Literature Review

Sengottaiyan and Ambika (2013) highlighted the fertilizer industry in India, noting that the

country is one of the largest producers and consumers of fertilizers globally. They emphasized the need to adopt technologically advanced manufacturing processes and introduce innovative, modern products. Similarly, Singh (2013) underscored the critical role of chemical fertilizers in achieving self-reliance in food grain production. His research explored various aspects such as the demand and supply dynamics, consumption patterns, and the growth factors influencing the fertilizer sector in India.

Nirali J Kantharia (2020) A study published in the International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews (Vol. 7, Issue 1, March 2020) focused on profitability analysis in the power sector, with a specific emphasis on a selected company. The primary objective of the research was to assess the company's growth and profitability over time. The methodology involved analyzing key financial indicators such as the Net Profit Ratio, Operating Profit Ratio, and Rate of Return. The study concluded that the selected power-generating firm's profitability had a direct impact on its growth trajectory, highlighting the importance of efficient financial management for sustainable performance.

Statement of the Problem

The profitability of fertilizer companies is crucial for their sustainability and growth, impacting not only the companies themselves but also the agricultural sector they serve. Despite the significance of this industry in Tamil Nadu, there is limited research focusing on the comparative profitability of players like Southern Petrochemicals Industries Corporation (SPIC) and Madras Fertilizers Limited (MFL). This lack of comprehensive analysis raises concerns about the financial performance and operational efficiency of these companies in a competitive market. Fluctuations in profitability ratios may indicate underlying operational issues, management inefficiencies, or challenges in adapting to market dynamics.

Objective

The objective of this research is to conduct a profitability analysis of fertilizer companies.

1. To analyze the profitability performance of selected fertilizer companies in Tamil Nadu.
2. To compare the profitability performance of the selected companies.

Research Methodology

- a) **Data Collection**-Secondary data is collected from the annual financial reports of the companies, websites, journals, and government publications for the relevant period.
- b) **Sample Selection**-The two prominent fertilizer companies in Tamil Nadu: Southern Petrochemicals Industries Corporation (SPIC) and Madras Fertilizers Limited (MFL). These companies were selected based on their significant market presence.
- c) **Time Period of Study**-The financial data is analyzed over the period from 2019-20 to 2023-24.
- d) **Tools for Analysis**-The analysis various financial ratios, including Operating Profit Ratio, Net Profit

Ratio, Return on Net Worth, Total Debt/Equity, and Return on Assets, to evaluate the profitability of SPIC and MFL statistical methods such as two-way ANOVA will be utilized to determine significant differences in profitability metrics between the companies and across the selected time period.

- e) **Limitations**-The study focuses only on selected fertilizer companies in Tamil Nadu and is limited to the availability and reliability of secondary data.

Company Profile

Madras Fertilizers Limited (MFL)

MFL established in 1966, is a public sector enterprise engaged in the manufacturing and marketing of ammonia, urea, and complex fertilizers. Headquartered in Chennai, it focuses on sustainable agriculture through efficient fertilizer production. The company caters primarily to the agricultural sector in Tamil Nadu and neighboring states. MFL promotes eco-friendly practices and maintains government partnerships to boost productivity.

Southern Petrochemical Industries Corporation (SPIC)

-Founded in 1969 and based in Chennai, SPIC is a leading fertilizer manufacturer in India, producing urea and other agro-based products. The company emphasizes sustainable development and caters to both domestic and international markets. SPIC actively promotes efficient farming practices and supports agricultural innovation. It has diversified interests in petrochemicals, engineering, and power.

Profitability Analysis- Profitability analysis evaluates a company's ability to generate profits relative to its revenue, assets, and equity. It helps assess the efficiency of operations, cost management, and financial performance. This analysis provides insights into the sustainability and competitiveness of a business in the market.

Table 1: Profitability Analysis

Year	Operating Profit ratio		Net Profit Ratio		Return on Net worth		Total Debt/Equity		Return on Assets	
	MFL	SPIC	MFL	SPIC	MFL	SPIC	MFL	SPIC	MFL	SPIC
2019-20	-1.42	5.92	-10.58	2.73	0.00	14.21	-2.85	0.70	-8.82	2.76
2020-21	8.64	6.48	0.18	3.39	-0.41	11.27	-1.98	0.23	0.23	3.13
2021-22	11.69	10.61	7.03	7.49	-32.06	22.85	-3.43	0.49	8.48	8.71
2022-23	9.76	13.23	5.37	10.05	-64.55	32.10	-5.20	0.45	9.98	13.53
2023-24	6.47	13.77	0.24	4.52	-2.93	9.24	-8.35	0.49	0.27	5.36
Minimum	-1.42	5.92	-10.58	2.73	-64.55	9.24	-8.35	0.23	-8.82	2.76
Maximum	11.69	13.77	7.03	10.05	0.00	32.10	-1.98	0.70	9.98	13.53
Mean	7.03	10.00	0.45	5.64	-19.99	17.93	-4.36	0.47	2.03	6.70
S D	5.09	3.68	6.88	3.07	28.31	9.47	2.52	0.17	7.56	4.49
Skewness	-1.51	-0.20	-1.20	0.80	-1.28	0.96	-1.20	-0.21	-0.50	1.00
Kurtosis	2.51	-2.92	1.63	-1.09	0.48	-0.43	1.01	1.83	-0.52	-0.02

Source: Money control.

Table 1 The profitability analysis between MFL and SPIC over the years 2019-20 to 2023-24 reveals notable differences in their financial performance. MFL’s operating profit ratio shows significant fluctuation, starting at a negative -1.42% in 2019-20 and peaking at 11.69% in 2021-22, indicating inconsistent operational efficiency. In contrast, SPIC maintains steady growth in operating profits, reaching 13.77% in 2023-24, reflecting better operational stability. A similar trend is observed in the net profit ratio, where MFL exhibits volatility, with a low of -10.58% in 2019-20 and modest recovery to 0.24% in 2023-24. SPIC consistently posts positive net profits, peaking at 10.05% in 2022-23, demonstrating stronger profitability.

MFL's return on net worth is highly negative in several years, indicating poor returns for shareholders, with the lowest being -64.55% in 2022-23. In contrast, SPIC performs significantly better, with a peak return on net worth of 32.10% in the same year. The debt-to-equity ratio for MFL is negative throughout, suggesting high debt reliance or negative equity, while SPIC manages its debt efficiently with low, positive ratios. MFL also struggles in return on assets, recording negative returns in most years, which indicates inefficient utilization of its assets. Meanwhile, SPIC achieves consistent positive returns, with the

highest being 13.53% in 2022-23.

SPIC consistently outperforms MFL in profitability metrics, with higher means and lower variability, as reflected by the standard deviation. MFL shows higher variability in performance, indicating instability. The skewness for MFL is negative, reflecting a tendency towards lower performance, whereas SPIC exhibits a more balanced skew, hinting at stable financial trends. Lastly, kurtosis values show that SPIC’s profitability metrics have fewer extreme variations compared to MFL. In summary, SPIC demonstrates superior financial management and stability, whereas MFL faces challenges with volatility, negative returns, and inconsistent financial performance across the years.

Operating Profit Ratio-Operating profit, often referred to as operating income or EBIT (Earnings before Interest and Taxes), measures a company's profitability from its core business operations. It excludes non-operating income and expenses, providing a clear view of how well a company generates profit from its regular business activities.

H₀: There is no significant difference of the mean values of operating profit ratio among the fertilizer company with respect to between years and between companies.

Table 2: Operating Profit Ratio (Two-Way ANOVA)

Sources of Variance	Sum of Squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean Square variance	F Ratio	'p' Value
Between Years	117.124	4	29.281	2.9	0.163523
Between Companies	22.112	1	22.112	2.19	0.213009
Error	40.408	4	10.102		
Total	179.643	9			

Source: Data calculated; **Note:** Significant at 5% Level.

Table 2 indicate that the p-values for both the between years ($p = 0.163523$) and between companies ($p = 0.213009$) are greater than the significance level of 0.05. Therefore, we fail to reject the null hypothesis (H_0), suggesting that there is no significant difference in the operating profit ratio between the years or the companies analyzed. The F-ratios of 2.9 and 2.19 further support this conclusion, indicating that the variation between groups is not statistically significant. These results imply that operating profit ratios remain consistent across the years and companies.

Net Profit Ratio- The net profit ratio, also known as net profit margin, measures a company's profitability by comparing net profit to total revenue. This ratio reflects the percentage of revenue that remains as profit after all expenses, taxes, and costs have been deducted, providing insights into a company's financial efficiency.

H_0 : There is no significant difference of the mean values of net profit ratio among the fertilizer company with respect to between years and between companies.

Table 3: NET profit ratio (TWO-WAY ANOVA)

Sources of Variance	Sum of Squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean Square variance	F Ratio	'p' Value
Between Years	180.278	4	45.070	3.86	0.10959
Between Companies	67.288	1	67.288	5.77	0.074189
Error	46.658	4	11.664		
Total	294.225	9			

Source: Data calculated; **Note:** Significant at 5% Level.

Table 3 show that the p-values for both the between years ($p = 0.10959$) and between companies ($p = 0.074189$) are greater than the significance level of 0.05. Consequently, we fail to reject the null hypothesis (H_0), indicating no significant difference in the net profit ratio across different years and companies. The F-ratios of 3.86 and 5.77 suggest that the variability between groups is not statistically significant at the 5% level. Overall, these findings imply that the net profit ratios remain consistent over the analyzed time period and

among the companies in the study.

Net Worth-Net worth represents the total value of an individual's or entity's assets minus their liabilities, providing a snapshot of financial health. It serves as a indicator of financial stability and is often used to assess the overall economic position of a business or individual.

H_0 : There is no significant difference of the mean values of net worth among the fertilizer company with respect to between years and between companies.

Table 4: Net worth (TWO-WAY ANOVA)

Sources of Variance	Sum of Squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean Square variance	F Ratio	'p' Value
Between Years	738.185	4	184.546	0.261	0.889214
Between Companies	3595.574	1	3595.574	5.09	0.087055
Error	2825.819	4	706.455		
Total	7159.578	9			

Source : Data calculated; Note: P Significant at 5% Level.

Table 4 reveal that the p-value for the between years ($p = 0.889214$) is significantly higher than the 0.05 level, leading us to fail to reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and indicating no significant difference in net worth across different years. Conversely, the p-value for the between companies ($p = 0.087055$) is also greater than 0.05, suggesting no significant difference at the 5% level in net worth among the companies. The F-ratios of 0.261 and 5.09 further support this conclusion, with the former indicating minimal variability over years. These imply that net worth remains relatively consistent across both the years analyzed and the companies.

Debt Equity-The debt-to-equity ratio is a financial metric that compares a company's total liabilities to its shareholder equity, indicating the proportion of financing sourced from creditors versus owners. This ratio helps assess financial leverage and the risk associated with a company's capital structure, reflecting how much debt is used to fund operations relative to equity.

H₀: There is no significant difference of the mean values of debt equity among the fertilizer company with respect to between years and between companies.

Table: 5 Debt Equity (TWO-WAY ANOVA)

Sources of Variance	Sum of Squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean Square variance	F Ratio	'p' Value
Between Years	12.505	4	3.126	0.96	0.515304
Between Companies	58.419	1	58.419	17.91	0.013348
Error	13.042	4	3.260		
Total	83.966	9			

Source: Data calculated; Note: Significant at 5% Level.

Table 5 indicate that the p-value for the between years ($p = 0.515304$) is much higher than the significance level of 0.05, leading us to fail to reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and suggesting no significant difference in the debt-to-equity ratio across different years. In contrast, the p-value for the between companies ($p = 0.013348$) is below 0.05, indicating a significant difference at the 5% level in the debt-to-equity ratios among the companies. The F-ratio of 17.91 for the between companies further confirms this significant variation. these findings suggest that while debt-to-equity ratios do not vary significantly over the years, there are meaningful differences among the

companies.

Return on Asset- Return on Assets (ROA) is a financial metric that indicates how efficiently a company uses its assets to generate profit, calculated by dividing net income by total assets. This ratio helps investors and management assess the effectiveness of asset utilization in driving profitability, reflecting operational efficiency.

H₀: There is no significant difference of the mean values of return on asset among the fertilizer company with respect to between years and between companies.

Table 6: Return On Asset (TWO-WAY ANOVA)

Sources of Variance	Sum of Squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean Square variance	F Ratio	'p' Value
Between Years	273.605	4	68.401	7.59	0.037502
Between Companies	54.522	1	54.522	6.06	0.069564
Error	36.013	4	9.003		
Total	364.140	9			

Source: Data calculated; Note: Significant at 5% Level.

Table 6 show that the p-value for the between years ($p = 0.037502$) is less than the significance level of 0.05, allowing us to reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and indicating a significant difference in the return on assets across different years. In contrast, the p-value for the between companies ($p = 0.069564$) is greater than 0.05, leading us to fail to reject the null hypothesis regarding differences among companies. The F-ratios of 7.59 and 6.06 support these conclusions, with the former indicating considerable variability over the years. That return on assets has significantly changed over the years, but not significantly among the companies analyzed.

Findings

- MFL's operating profit ratio fluctuated significantly, indicating inconsistent operational performance.
- SPIC demonstrated a steady increase in its operating profit ratio, showcasing efficiency and stability.
- MFL exhibited high volatility in its net profit ratio, reflecting challenges in managing expenses relative to revenue.
- SPIC consistently achieved positive net profit ratios, peaking in 2022-23, indicating effective cost management.
- MFL's return on net worth was negative in several years, signaling poor returns for shareholders.
- SPIC achieved a peak return on net worth of 32.10%, suggesting better shareholder value creation.
- MFL's debt-to-equity ratio remained negative, showing a high reliance on debt or negative equity.

- SPIC maintained low, positive debt-to-equity ratios, indicating efficient debt management.
- MFL recorded negative returns on assets in most years, reflecting inefficient asset utilization.
- SPIC achieved consistent positive returns on assets, highlighting effective asset management.
- Two-way ANOVA results showed no significant differences in operating and net profit ratios between the companies and years.
- Significant variability was found in debt-to-equity ratios, highlighting differences in capital structure.
- Return on assets showed significant fluctuations across years, indicating variations in operational efficiency.
- MFL displayed higher variability in profitability metrics, indicating financial instability.
- Skewness and kurtosis indicated lower performance with extreme variations for MFL, while SPIC exhibited more stable financial trends.

Suggestions:

- ❖ MFL should implement cost management strategies to stabilize operating and net profit ratios.
- ❖ MFL should consider debt restructuring to improve its debt-to-equity ratio and financial stability.
- ❖ Both companies should explore ways to optimize asset utilization to improve returns on assets.
- ❖ SPIC should continue refining operational processes to enhance efficiency.

- ❖ Both companies should conduct regular financial analyses to monitor profitability and adjust strategies.
- ❖ MFL should invest in technology to streamline operations and improve profitability.
- ❖ MFL should explore new revenue streams or diversify product offerings to stabilize performance.
- ❖ Financial training for management can improve decision-making regarding cost control and revenue generation.
- ❖ Both companies should benchmark their performance against competitors to identify areas for improvement.
- ❖ SPIC should enhance communication with shareholders on strategies to improve returns.
- ❖ MFL should prioritize cash flow management to ensure liquidity and financial health.
- ❖ Both companies should review financial policies regularly to adapt to market changes.
- ❖ Implementing robust risk management practices can help both companies mitigate financial uncertainties.
- ❖ MFL could consider forming joint ventures to leverage resources and enhance profitability.
- ❖ Both companies should focus on sustainable practices to improve financial performance and brand reputation.

Conclusion

The profitability analysis of Southern Petrochemicals Industries Corporation (SPIC) and Madras Fertilizers Limited (MFL) over the period from 2019-20 to 2023-24 reveals significant disparities in financial performance. SPIC consistently outperformed MFL across profitability metrics, demonstrating operational stability and effective management of resources. In contrast, MFL faced challenges with high volatility in its profitability ratios, negative returns, and reliance on debt, suggesting an urgent need for strategic intervention. The statistical analyses indicated no significant differences in operating and net profit ratios between the two companies; however, significant variability in the debt-to-equity ratio highlights differing capital structures. The insights gleaned from this study

underline the importance of adopting effective financial strategies and operational improvements to enhance profitability in the fertilizer sector.

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